

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

PROCEEDINGS OF THE CONFERENCE

January 15, 2026
UWED
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

University of World Economy and Diplomacy

SAMEIR-2026

International Scientific and Practical Conference

**SYSTEM ANALYSIS
AND MODELING IN ECONOMY
AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS**

The conference is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

PROCEEDINGS

(Conference Proceedings)

January 15, 2026
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International Scientific and Practical Conference – SAMEIR-2026

SYSTEM ANALYSIS AND MODELING IN ECONOMY AND INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

The University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED) hosted the International Scientific and Practical Conference “System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations (SAMEIR-2026)” on January 15, 2026, in Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

The **main goal** of the conference was to bring together researchers, scholars, policy makers, and experts to discuss current scientific and practical issues related to system analysis and modeling of socio-economic and international processes. Particular emphasis was placed on the application of quantitative, mathematical, and computational methods, as well as on the development of interdisciplinary approaches to the analysis of economic dynamics, international relations, and global challenges.

Key Themes of the Conference:

- **System Analysis and Economic Modeling:** mathematical and econometric models in the world economy, analysis of structural changes, and forecasting of macroeconomic and financial indicator.
- **International Relations and World Politics:** quantitative methods for analyzing international processes, modeling of conflicts and cooperation, geopolitical forecasting, and risk assessment.
- **Mathematical and Computer Modeling:** methods of applied and computational mathematics, simulation and stochastic modeling, optimization and control of complex socio-economic systems.
- **Artificial Intelligence and Big Data:** applications of machine learning, artificial intelligence, and big data analytics in economic and international studies.
- **Sustainable Development and Global Security:** economic, environmental, and energy aspects of sustainable development, system approaches to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and issues of information and digital security.

The event was conducted in a **hybrid format** with participation in **English, Russian, and Uzbek**. The conference provided a high-level platform for **scientific exchange, networking, and policy dialogue**.

The authors are solely responsible for the content and accuracy of their articles

Dedicated to the 75th Anniversary of Professor Abdujabbor Rasulov

The International Scientific and Practical Conference “*System Analysis and Modeling in Economy and International Relations*” is dedicated to the 75th anniversary of **Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov**, an outstanding scientist, educator, and founder of a recognized scientific school in the fields of system analysis, mathematical and stochastic modeling.

Professor Rasulov’s academic career spans more than five decades and is inseparably connected with the development of applied mathematics, computational methods, and their practical implementation in economic and socio-economic research. His fundamental contributions to the theory and application of Monte Carlo methods, numerical solutions of linear and nonlinear boundary value problems, and stochastic modeling have gained wide recognition both in Uzbekistan and internationally.

A special place in Professor Rasulov’s professional life belongs to the **University of World Economy and Diplomacy (UWED)**. Since the founding of the University, he has played a decisive role in shaping its scientific and academic profile. As Head of Department, Dean of Faculty, Vice-Rector for Research, and Professor, he consistently promoted a multidisciplinary approach, integrating mathematical modeling, system analysis, and quantitative methods into the study of economics, international relations, and diplomacy. This approach has become one of the distinctive features of UWED’s academic tradition.

Professor Rasulov is not only a prominent researcher, but also an exceptional mentor. Under his supervision, numerous PhD and Doctoral dissertations have been successfully defended. Many of his former students currently hold leading academic and administrative positions, continuing and developing the scientific traditions established by their mentor. The permanent scientific seminar initiated by Professor Rasulov has become an essential institutional platform at UWED, where dissertation research in mathematical modeling and system analysis is regularly presented, discussed, and refined, contributing to the formation of a rigorous and open academic environment.

Professor Rasulov’s extensive international collaborations with research centers and universities in the United States, Japan, Europe, and Asia have significantly strengthened UWED’s global academic presence. His active participation in international research

projects, conferences, editorial boards of leading scientific journals, and grant programs has contributed to the integration of national scientific research into the global academic community.

The present conference brings together researchers from different countries and disciplines, reflecting the breadth of scientific interests inspired by Professor Rasulov's work. The papers included in this volume address contemporary problems of system analysis, mathematical modeling, and their applications in economics and international relations, continuing the scholarly dialogue initiated and supported by Professor Rasulov over many years.

This volume is not only a collection of scientific papers, but also a tribute to Professor Abdujabbor Sattarovich Rasulov's lifelong dedication to science, education, and the development of future generations of scholars. The Organizing Committee expresses its deep respect and sincere gratitude to Professor Rasulov for his invaluable contribution to academic science and wishes him good health, continued creative inspiration, and further success in his scholarly endeavors.

Functional Central Limit Theorem for Random Fields with Values in Some Infinite Dimensional Spaces

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Let $\{X_i, i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be a sequence of random variables taking values in a separable Hilbert space H endowed with the inner product (\cdot, \cdot) and the corresponding norm $\|\cdot\| = \sqrt{(\cdot, \cdot)}$. Assume that $\{X_i, i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ can be represented as

$$X_i = f(\varepsilon_{i-s}), \quad s \in \mathbb{Z}, i \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (1)$$

where $\{\varepsilon_j, j \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ is a sequence of independent and identically distributed random variables taking values in H and f is a measurable function (for real-valued case see [1], [2]).

Let $\{\varepsilon'_j, j \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be an independent copy of $\{\varepsilon_j, j \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ and

$$X_i^* = f(\varepsilon_{i-s}^*), \quad s \in \mathbb{Z},$$

where

$$\varepsilon_j^* = \begin{cases} \varepsilon_j, & j \neq 0, \\ \varepsilon'_j, & j = 0. \end{cases}$$

Introduce the following notation:

$\{e_j, j \geq 1\}$ - an orthonormal basis of H ,

$$X_i = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} X_i^{(j)} e_j,$$

$$S_n = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i \in \Gamma_n} X_i, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, n,$$

$$S_n(t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{n}} \sum_{i=1}^{[nt]} X_i, \quad t \in [0, 1],$$

$$t_{ij} = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} E S_n^{(i)} S_n^{(j)}, \quad i, j = 1, 2, \dots,$$

$$\delta_{ij} = \sqrt{E(X_i^{(j)} - X_i^{*(j)})^2}.$$

$$\Delta_p(j) = \sum_{t \in \mathbb{Z}} \delta_j(t, p).$$

Our aim is to prove functional central limit theorem for $\{X_i, i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$. Central limit theorems were proved in [3],[4].

Theorem 1. Let $\{X_i, i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be a centered, sequence of random variables taking values in a separable Hilbert space H and satisfying the following conditions

$$\sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} \delta_{ij} < \infty, \quad j = 1, 2,$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_{ii} < \infty, \quad t_{jj} > 0 \quad j = 1, 2, \dots,$$

Then the following weak convergence holds

$$S_n(t) \Rightarrow W(t) \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

where $W(t)$, $t \in [0, 1]$ is a Brownian motion with values in H and $W(1)$, is a Gaussian random variable with values in H with mean zero and covariance matrix $T = (t_{ij})$. Analogous results are obtained for the sequences with values in ℓ_p ($1 \leq p \leq 2$) (a space of the sequences $x = (x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots)$ such that $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |x^{(i)}|^p < \infty$ with a norm $\|x\| = \left(\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} |x^{(i)}|^p \right)^{\frac{1}{p}}$ and c_0 (a space of all sequences $x = (x^{(1)}, x^{(2)}, \dots)$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x^{(n)} = 0$ with a norm $\|x\| = \sup_i |x^{(i)}|$).

In ℓ_p ($1 \leq p \leq 2$) and c_0 spaces as a basis $\{e_j, j \geq 1\}$ we take a standard basis i.e. $e_j = (0, 0, \dots, 1, 0, \dots)$ where i -th component is 1 and others are 0. In the next theorems we use above notation.

Theorem 2. Let $\{X_i, i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be a centered, sequence of random variables taking values in ℓ_p ($1 \leq p \leq 2$) and satisfying the following conditions

$$\sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} \delta_{ij} < \infty, \quad j = 1, 2,$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_{ii}^{\frac{p}{2}} < \infty, \quad t_{jj} = 1, 2, \dots,$$

Then the following weak convergence holds

$$S_n(t) \Rightarrow W(t) \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

where $W(t)$, $t \in [0, 1]$ is a Brownian motion with values in ℓ_p ($1 \leq p \leq 2$) and $W(1)$ is a Gaussian random variable with values in ℓ_p ($1 \leq p \leq 2$) with mean zero and covariance matrix $T = (t_{ij})$.

Theorem 3. Let $\{X_i, i \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ be a centered, sequence of random variables taking values in c_0 and satisfying the following conditions

$$\sum_{i \in \mathbb{Z}} \delta_{ij} < \infty, \quad j = 1, 2,$$

$$\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} t_{ii} < \infty,$$

Then the following weak convergence holds

$$S_n(t) \Rightarrow W(t) \quad \text{as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

where $W(t)$, $t \in [0, 1]$ is a Brownian motion with values in c_0 and $W(1)$ is a Gaussian random variable with values in c_0 with mean zero and covariance matrix $T = (t_{ij})$.

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